

GENDER ISSUES IN TRANSLATION

Xojimatova Muharramxon

Second year student of Fergana State University, FFL

Guiding and translating activities.

E-mail: muharramxon05@gmail.com

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Abstract. Translation is complex process as it has plenty of challenging aspects to accomplish while transforming source text into another language. In this article, some problematic issues of translation will be discussed and particularly, more information about gender issues in translation is being presented in order to solve them in proper way. Moreover, the theme is important for translators who want to be professional in their own field to ensure that conveying each word from source language to target language in correct style that writer of original text created.

Key words: translation, gender, insufficient responsibility, Source and Target language (TL and SL), transforming words, features of men and women, essence of understanding writer.

ГЕНДЕРНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ В ПЕРЕВОДЕ

Аннотация. Перевод — это сложный процесс, поскольку он требует выполнения множества сложных аспектов при преобразовании исходного текста на другой язык. В этой статье будут обсуждаться некоторые проблемные вопросы перевода и, в частности, представлена дополнительная информация о гендерных проблемах перевода для их правильного решения. Более того, тема важна для переводчиков, которые хотят быть профессионалами в своей области, чтобы гарантировать передачу каждого слова с исходного языка на целевой язык в правильном стиле, созданном автором оригинального текста.

Ключевые слова: перевод, пол, недостаточная ответственность, исходный и целевой язык (ЯЯ и ЯЯ), слова-трансформеры, особенности мужчины и женщины, сущность понимания писателя.

Introduction. In daily lives, it is possible to clash a lot with issues of gender inequality, such as whether women are superior to men or men have more opportunities rather than women. Moreover, such problems appear in terms of language and field of translation. Many researches show that, female and male translators can share similar interpreting styles in regard to dimensional aspects of source texts, featured by informative production, non-narrative concerns and abstract

information. They use homogeneous methods while translating clear and formal parts of their interpreting text. However, when it comes to shape description of images of heroes, different translating styles might be distinguished by translators. That is, male and female translators transform expression and words in source language according to their masculine and feminine horizons. It is fact that, men tend to be more realistic and appropriate to the common rights of life and rather women tend to be more expressive and emotional for everything that they meet. That`s why it can impact even to the issues of translation based on divorce opinions of male and female translators. Notion of style refers to translator`s choice of the type of words, phrases that can be served as materials to translate and use of specific strategies, including use of adjectives, explaining misunderstandable words in the process of translation. Additionally, after some studies, approaching source text in terms of gender equality also can be included by the translator`s style in order to translate everything close to the original version of text that is written by whether male or female writer. Because, translators are required to convey ST into TL in completely true way without losing the original expressiveness and stylistic features while translating the given text. Although there are some differences, not any proof found that showed gender might affect translation works significantly. Translators are required to be attentive while transforming each word from target language into source language as every expression might have unique and essence meaning that must be brought in order to produce on the minds of readers as nearly as possible to the readers on its original text. Translators have no any opportunity to add something to the source text(ST) because it should be as original as source language. However, translators tend to add some extra components that original writer has not create and even this leads to changing of word meanings. Especially, female translators might put expressive word and phrases that writer didn`t utilize. In this case, gender issues play its role significantly in translation studies. Although it is studied rarely, it becomes a new field to be learned more. It is linked to some aspect such as language itself, the variations between male and female languages.

Main part. The topic of gender consists of the differences between women and men, who exist in society, which constitute the peculiarities of the representatives of these two groups. These meditations are considered to be "masculine" and "feminine". Also, it should be noted that, gender issues include five gender markers, they are — phonetic, grammatical, lexical, morphological and thematic markers. They are defined according to their functions during translation. Moreover, men and women translate them differently, for example, in terms of lexical gender, main variations are that, male translators use words with least emotional state and they accustomed to utilize a large number of abstract nouns. When it comes to women, they often use interjections like “ouch!”,

“oh”, “ah!”. Unless the males, female translators tend to practice more expressive and emotional phrases in order to make translated text more stylistic way. *Grammatical gender* is a system of noun classification found in many languages. In some languages, such as Spanish and French, every noun is assigned a gender, either masculine or feminine. In other languages, such as German, there are three genders: masculine, feminine, and neuter. When translating from a language with grammatical gender to a language without it, the translator must decide how to handle the gender of the nouns. During translation process, translators can use some *necessary strategies* to convey grammatical gender of text. *First* one is ignoring the gender: Some translators choose to simply ignore the gender of the nouns and use the same gender for all nouns in the target language. This can lead to awkward or confusing sentences, but it is sometimes necessary if the target language does not have a system of grammatical gender. *Second* one is using the natural gender: If the gender of the noun corresponds to the natural gender of the object it represents (e.g. "man" is masculine in many languages), then the translator can use the appropriate gender in the target language. Last method is using an equivalent noun: If there is no equivalent noun in the target language with the same gender as the source language noun, the translator may need to use a different noun that conveys the same meaning but has a different gender. In short, when translating from a language with grammatical gender to a language without it, translators must carefully consider how to handle the gender of the nouns in order to produce an accurate and natural-sounding translation. *Cultural gender* is also important in translation field. The translation process may give increase to other problems as a result of the gender connotations in which speakers may perceive the world. This is especially true with respect to metaphors and personifications, and an ideologically determined clash may occur if a specific gender in one language connotes certain properties, while the translated word in the target language belongs to another gender that conveys quite different connotations. Additionally, cultural gender in translation refers to the way that gender is expressed and understood in different cultures and languages, and how this can affect the translation of texts. As an evidence, in some languages, there may be various words or forms of address for men and women, or certain activities or professions may be associated with a particular gender. Translators need to be aware of these cultural differences and make appropriate choices when translating texts to ensure that the intended meaning is conveyed into the TL. *Thematic gender* in translation means the way gender is portrayed and represented in translated texts. This can involve the transformation of pronouns, titles, and other gendered language, as well as the translation of cultural norms and expectations. One important aspect of thematic gender in translation is the way that gender can impact the meaning and interpretation of a text. For instance,

a text that uses gendered language to reinforce traditional gender roles may be translated in a way that challenges those roles, leading to a different interpretation of the text. While translation process, translators must be careful translating cultural, social norms of SL, even in some cases, they have to learn aspects of cultural gender like, identity, race, ethnicity and others. According to many researches, it is defined that, there are several differences between male and female translators in terms of gender issues in translation, style and methods of translation and other dynamic units.

Male translator	Female translator
1. Uses words with the least emotional, expressive state.	1. Often uses expressive interjections
2. Put the use of a large amount of abstract nouns.	2. Uses more explanations, definitions of phrase in order to express each word in easy way.
3. Significantly reduces the text volume when translating.	3. Tends to use “prestigious” stylistically elevated forms, clichés, bookish lexicon.
4. Gives preference to expressive, especially stylistically lowered means.	4. Uses connotatively neutral words and expressions, euphemisms.
5. More often uses informative and persistent statements such as “obviously”, “evidently”, “undoubtedly”, “naturally”.	5. Actively uses of phraseological units.

In most cases, both male and female translators convey ST into the TL according to their masculine and feminine outlooks. As most people know that, women writers try to describe physiological sides of men while writing novels or books, they tend to portray strength, potency and force of them. However, if that book would be translated by male translator, he might ignore this kind of physiological parts as they may not feel as attentively as women the heroes. This can lead to loss of original features of source text in terms of some images of heroes of translated text. Such condition can be occurred by female translators, they also ignore some characteristics of male heroines that might be described by male writer. Usually, male writers try to focus on describing elegance of women, like their lips, faces, eyes and etc. But, while translation process, female translators might miss these features of portrayed images by male writer.

Conclusion. Generally, translation is process of conveying words from source language into target language without losing any lexical, semantic characteristics that created by writer.

These features can include gender issues, types of transformation, equivalence in translation and others. Gender issues are more important in this field in owing to translate ST in proper intended way. Translators have more responsibilities on their shoulders, as they, at the same time, not only convey words but also the cultural and social values of one nation. In that case, gender issues identify sufficient skills of translators. They should be aware of referring to those matters since they are considered as common problems of translation.

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